

Reply to Altaba (2025): Corrections to the article “Taxonomic revision of the Iberian Allognathini (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Helicidae)”

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Abstract

A thorough review is conducted of the article titled "Taxonomic revision of the Iberian Allognathini (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Helicidae)" authored by Cristian R. Altaba and published in *Folia Conchylologica*. The analysis reveals a substantial number of inaccuracies, errors, misrepresentations of pre-existing scientific evidence, and unfounded taxonomic conclusions.

Keywords

Iberus, review, taxonomy, unfounded conclusions

Introduction

The species diversity of the genus *Iberus* Monfort, 1810 is still a topic of debate. The first relevant taxonomic review on this genus was carried out by García San Nicolás (1957) and it was based on morphological characters. Fifty years later, Elejalde et al. (2008a, b) reevaluated the genus using molecular analyses based on the sequencing of the cytochrome oxidase subunit I (COI) and RNA ribosomal 16S (16S rRNA). Elejalde et al. demonstrated that morphology is of limited use in delimiting *Iberus* species, as this genus encompasses both cryptic species with very similar morphologies and highly polymorphic species with significantly different shells (reviewed in Liétor et al., 2025a). To clarify the taxonomy of the genus *Iberus*, we conducted a comprehensive study over 20 years, sampling the genus at 1,763 points across Spain, measuring 19,692 shells (11 morphometric parameters for each), and performing genetic analyses on 72 key samples based on two mitochondrial and one nuclear gene fragment. As a result, a reliable taxonomy has been constructed, particularly at the lower taxonomic level such as for species (Liétor et al., 2025a).

At the end of March 2025, issue 74 of the journal *Folia Conchylologica* is published with a single article titled "Taxonomic revision of the Iberian Allognathini (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Helicidae)", authored by Cristian R. Altaba, affiliated with the Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and

Natural Environment, Government of the Balearic Islands, and the Research Group on Human Evolution and Cognition (EVOCOG), University of the Balearic Islands, Spain.

This review employs a phylogenetic analysis based on published partial COI sequences. Based on this analysis, Cristian R. Altaba's (hereafter, CRA) concludes that the genus *Iberus* is paraphyletic and proposes splitting the genus into several new genera. More precisely, CRA defines 6 new subtribes, 5 new genera, 5 new subgenera, 7 new species, and 6 new subspecies for the land snails of the tribe Allognathini.

Given the debate on the taxonomy of this genus, any well-built and documented study would be welcomed to clarify the taxonomy of this particular genus. However, CRA's study fails to do so due to a fundamental issue as his phylogenetic tree contradicts well established phylogenies (Elejalde et al., 2008a, b; Neiber et al., 2021; Liétor et al., 2025a). As already mentioned, this phylogeny relies on a single mitochondrial gene, whereas the previous studies incorporated combined genetic data from multiple genes including nuclear ones, making their findings more robust than CRA's review. CRA's argument that incorporating additional mitochondrial and nuclear DNA data would introduce noise rather than valuable information is misguided and astonishing. In fact, CRA's argument contradicts contemporary phylogenetic knowledge as well as the whole field of phylogenomics. Today it is widely accepted that concatenating multiple mitochondrial and nuclear genes is scientifically more appropriate for constructing phylogenies and describing new taxa, as it provides a more comprehensive and accurate perspective on evolutionary relationships (e.g., Springer et al., 2001; Ossa et al., 2014). That is why the concatenation of nuclear and mitochondrial genes has become a widespread practice in taxonomic studies of terrestrial gastropods (e.g. Neiber et al., 2017; Chueca et al., 2018; Brozzo et al., 2020). Moreover, species delimitation based solely on COI sequences can be misleading at times, due to issues like introgression and hybridization (e.g., Zhang et al., 2021).

CRA's article overlooks nearly all of the genetic sequences uploaded to GenBank by Liétor et al. (2024a-c, g, 2025a) and Tudela et al. (2024). However, Altaba relies on the sequences provided by the authors in Jowers et al. (2024) for *Tartessiberus cilbanus* Altaba and Ríos Jiménez, 2021. While it is reasonable to consider all available data when constructing a phylogenetic tree, CRA seems to selectively choose sequences based on a criterion that remains unclear to us. For our phylogenetic reconstruction, we employed maximum likelihood and Bayesian inference through analyses. According to our results, the clade corresponding to the genera outside the Iberian Peninsula (Balearic Islands, Maderia and the Canary Islands), merged into *Iberus* in CRA's study, lack any statistical support. In fact, Neiber et al. (2021) phylogeny, based on multiple genetic sequences recovered this clade as monophyletic and sister clade to *Iberus*. Our analyses do not recover CRA's findings, nor do previous studies; therefore, there is no statistical evidence supporting CRA's claim that the genus *Iberus* is paraphyletic.(also see Neiber et al., 2021). The low quality presentation and dreadful layout of tree make it almost impossible to understand topology and clade support. A significant question for CRA concerns the evolutionary rationale he would propose to explain the phylogenetic placement of the insular taxa within Iberian lineages—particularly with respect to the genera *Hemicycla* and *Lampadia*, from the Canary Islands and Madeira, respectively.

The Cytochrome Oxidase I (COI) gene is widely used in molecular biology, particularly for species identification through DNA barcoding. However, its utility diminishes at higher taxonomic levels, such as genera and families. This limitation arises because COI sequences often exhibit low variability among closely related genera, leading to insufficient resolution for accurate phylogenetic analyses at more ancestral nodes (e.g., Bai et al., 2020). Indeed, our phylogenetic tree analysis using MrBayes and RaXml, replicating CRA's topology, provides no support for the delineation of new genera—consistent with the findings of Elejalde et al. (2008a, b) and (Neiber

at al., 2021), both of which also found no genetic basis for defining supraspecific taxonomic ranks, based on other analyses such as BEAST, Maximum Parsimony, Maximum Likelihood and Bayesian Inference. Furthermore, CRA fails to provide any data on intra- and interspecific genetic distances, leaving the reader without an objective basis for evaluating his taxonomic proposals. This omission disregards the substantial body of published data available in Elejalde et al. (2008a), Liétor et al. (2024a–c, g; 2025a, b), Jowers et al. (2024), and Tudela et al. (2024). Genetic distance is a valuable tool in taxonomy, particularly in groups such as land snails, where cryptic species are common (e.g., Haase et al., 2003; Pfenninger and Schwenk, 2007; Mason et al., 2020).

In the absence of genetic distance data, CRA's supports his new taxa based on conchological traits that exhibit wide interpopulation variability and often even intrapopulation variability. These traits are not presented within the context of morphometric analyses but they rather consist of mere observations or assumptions made on what is presumably a very limited number of shells. There is a widespread consensus that morphology alone cannot be used in taxonomic studies of land snails (e.g., Pfenninger et al., 2006), which would be particularly inefficient in groups with numerous cryptic species, such as in the genus *Iberus*. Indeed, in studies on terrestrial gastropods, molecular data do not always align with conchological or anatomical data (e.g., Fiorentino et al., 2008). Furthermore, taxa that are almost indistinguishable in their shells may be genetically well separated or vice versa (Giusti and Manganelli, 1992; Alonso et al., 2006). Among helicids, there are notable examples of how the application of molecular methods often leads to changes in taxonomy that was previously based on morphology. For example, after conducting phylogenetic analyses, Neiber and Hausdorf (2015) reassigned two species, traditionally classified within the genus *Cepaea* based on shell morphology, to two different genera: *Caucasotachea* and *Macularia*. Similarly, molecular evidence led Korábek et al. (2016) to define a new divergent lineage for *Helix pomatia* populations, characterized by shells that fit the typical morphology of the species. Genetic analyses conducted by Korábek et al. (2022) repositioned *H. godetiana* within the genus *Helix*, thereby invalidating its previous placement within the genus *Maltzanella* based on morphological and anatomical data.

CRA's attempt to reassign nearly all taxonomic designations within the genus *Iberus* based primarily on vague conchological criteria is particularly problematic—especially given his complete disregard for the extensive hybridization documented within the genus, which routinely gives rise to intermediate shell forms (Liétor et al., 2025a). Remarkably, CRA even goes so far as to designate some of these intermediates as holotypes or neotypes for his newly proposed taxa.

The holotypes mentioned by CRA in his revision have not been deposited in any museum or institution but instead remain in his private collection. This practice infringes several recommendations of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN), which state that such pivotal referenced specimens should be easily accessible and traceable. The fact that our team contacted CRA in August 2024 to request photographs of the holotype of *Tartessiberus cilbanus* and received no response is further prove that the author does not ensure accessibility to his type material. It is also perplexing that the curator of the Balearic Museum of Natural Sciences, where CRA claims to have deposited one of the paratypes of *Tartessiberus cilbanus*, informed us that such a paratype does not exist.

Throughout his review, CRA attempts to discredit the results obtained by our team (Jowers et al., 2024; Liétor et al., 2024b, d, e, f; Tudela et al., 2024), seemingly with the aim of systematically prioritizing the resurrection of synonymized taxa and the description of new species—or the invalidation of existing ones—over robust scientific evidence, thereby contributing to taxonomic inflation. To this end, he frequently resorts to unnecessarily harsh language, using terms such as

“noise,” “equivocal methods,” “mistakes,” and “violations of the Code,” among other unsubstantiated criticisms. As we will demonstrate throughout this review, most of the arguments he puts forward to undermine these studies lack solid empirical support.

Lastly, in his criticism of our studies, CRA makes numerous mistakes, including selectively quoting and taking phrases out of context to suit his argument, ignoring key points necessary to understand the arguments expressed in our studies. That is why we find it appropriate to provide readers with an extensive list of corrections we deem applicable to CRA’s article. It is worth noting that J. Liétor provided significant batches of shells from the genus *Iberus* to CRA between 2015 and 2019, all of which were self-collected. Some of these shells have been used to define holotypes throughout CRA’s revision. Based on his extensive knowledge of the source populations of those holotypes, J. Liétor is well-positioned to carry out a well-founded analysis of many of the taxonomic decisions made by CRA.

Results and Discussion: A critical review of CRA’s paper

In the following pages, the signatory authors (SA) provide a comprehensive review of the numerous misinterpretations and erroneous conclusions made by CRA throughout his article.

COVER PHOTO

CRA: A specimen of *Iberus* from “the Cabo de Gata region” identified as *Iberus alonensis*.

SA: As will be explained later, the *Iberus* like-*alonensis* (according to Elejalde et al. 2008b) from Cabo de Gata has been recently described by Liétor et al. (2024a) as *Iberus xerophilus* Liétor, Jowers, Jódar, Galán-Luque and Tudela, 2024.

PAGE 2

Paragraph 2

CRA: “The current understanding of *Iberus* needs revision”.

SA: Liétor et al. (2025a) conducted an exhaustive review with over 1,700 sampling points, allowing them to define with unprecedented precision in European malacofauna the distribution of the taxa in the genus (Figure 1). This, along with a phylogenetic analysis using three genes (two mitochondrial and one nuclear) and a morphometric analysis of nearly 20,000 shells, provides a solid classification supported by 10 scientific publications (Jowers et al., 2024; Liétor et al., 2024a–f, 2025a, b; Tudela et al., 2024). In these publications, we carried out a thorough review of the taxonomic history of all the species, arguing with extraordinary detail the validity or invalidity of the classical names associated with the genus. Therefore, it is unclear why the current understanding of the *Iberus* genus needs revision, particularly given that CRA does not provide new genetic sequences, new geographical localities, or new contributions to the morphometric study of this genus. CRA’s revision appears to be focused on undermining our work and that of other researchers, such as Elejalde and coworkers, for which CRA provides flawed analyses and employs foul language, rather than contributing anything new to the taxonomy of the genus.

CRA: He states, referring to some *Iberus* species from the Betic area, that “their phylogenetic relationships remain unclear” accompanied by a series of bibliographic references: Rossmässler, 1854-1859; Schmidt, 1853, 1855; Kobelt, 1910; Serradell, 1912; Boettger, 1913; García San Nicolás, 1957; Cobos, 1980; Aparicio & Ramos, 1988; Elejalde et al., 2008a,b; Schileyko, 2006; Welter-Schultes, 2012; Polo Roldán, 2016; Jowers et al., 2024.

SA: Most of the studies listed there did not conduct any phylogenetic analysis. In the specific case of Jowers et al. (2024), the exact opposite of what the author claims was done: Jowers et al. demonstrate that the genus *Tartessiberus* is incorrect and a synonym of *Iberus*. Therefore, it helps clarify the taxonomy of the genus, rather than complicating it. This is the first in a series of attempts by CRA to revive the genus *Tartessiberus*, yet without presenting any convincing arguments. It is no coincidence that *Tartessiberus* was firstly described by CRA recently.

Figure 1. Map with all the sampling points recorded by our research team during nearly two decades of field research. On the right, the detailed area of Andalusia and Murcia regions (Southeastern Spain) with the highest sampling intensity is shown. Different colours indicate different species and subspecies, as identified in 10 scientific publications developed by the authors. All available information can be found in Liétor et al. (2025a). A significant portion of the points overlap at the displayed scale.

Paragraph 3

CRA: "Thus, the genus *Tartessiberus* Altaba & Ríos Jiménez, 2021 was erected for a highly specialized, phenotypically divergent species".

SA: This statement is incorrect. This genus was created without any genetic evidence, and phenotypically, it is so similar to other *Iberus* species that, for decades, it was considered an extension of *I. loxanus* in the province of Cádiz. Moreover, Jowers et al. (2024) show that the genetic divergent between this taxon and other *Iberus* species is not higher than among *Iberus* species.

Paragraph 4

CRA: "Although shells of all these land snails are relatively rich in taxonomically useful characters, there has been a general neglect of morphological data to evaluate the phylogenetic relationships within the Allognathini".

SA: It is not true that the morphological study of the genus *Iberus* has been neglected; quite the opposite, currently there is no other genus of the European terrestrial malacofauna with such an extensive morphological analysis as the one available for the genus *Iberus*: (i) In Liétor et al. (2024a-f, 2025a, b), Tudela et al. (2024), and Jowers et al. (2024), an extensive morphometric study was conducted. In total, the researchers collected 5 morphometric measurements (and 6 additional morphometric ratios) from nearly 20,000 shells. The statistical information derived from this vast dataset has enabled a highly reliable characterization of the typical shell morphology of all taxa within the genus *Iberus* and has been instrumental in clarifying its

taxonomy. (ii) Additionally, the coloration of the soft parts, including the mantle and foot, was used by us as a pioneering diagnostic criterion, which proves particularly useful for identifying hybrid populations. In Liétor et al. (2025a), the typical colorations of the mantle and foot have even been characterized for the 23 species of the genus *Iberus*. (iii) In our publications, particularly in Liétor et al. (2025a), a detailed review is presented of the banding pattern ratios (continuous vs. discontinuous bands) and the umbilicus aperture (partially open vs. closed) in *Iberus* species. All the morphological characters reviewed by us were used to support, along with the genetic and biogeographic evidence, our taxonomic conclusions.

CRA: “Shells of *Iberus* and allied genera are recognizable by their depressed shape, enlarged last whorl, more or less reflected lip, and medium to fairly large size (roughly from 17 to 45 mm in maximum diameter)”.

SA: This broad generalization makes no sense, as thousands of European land molluscs fit these criteria due to the considerable conchological diversity of *Iberus* and allied genera. See Annexes 1 and 2 in Liétor et al. (2025a).

PAGE 3

Paragraph 1

CRA: “Likewise, linear shell measurements predictably yield no reliable means of identifying specimens belonging to (even closely related) lineages delineated on a molecular tree (as attempted by Liétor et al., 2024a)”.

SA: This could be true when very few specimens are measured. But, as a general statement, it is wrong. When measuring a large number of objects, morphometric values become more reliable due to statistical principles that reduce variability and enhance precision. Research indicates that increasing the sample size improves the precision of reliability estimates, such as correlation coefficients and standard error of measurements. Larger samples consistently help to balance precision and efficiency in morphometric analyses. Liétor et al. repeatedly demonstrate across their publications that measuring hundreds of shells for a single species significantly reduces the coefficients of variation while substantially increasing the power of statistical tools.

Paragraph 2

CRA: “there is now a fairly high number of DNA sequences, produced by various teams working on the phylogenetics of *Iberus* and related taxa.”

SA: Sometimes, the sequences provided in the literature lack precise geographical information, images supporting both the animal and shell identity, and therefore, there is no traceability to ensure the species' correct identification. Likely due to its thoroughness, the work of Liétor et al. (2024a-f), Tudela et al. (2024), and Jowers et al. (2024) represent the only studies that have established a genetic sequence database linked to photographs of live animals and their shells, along with unequivocal collection data and subsequent identification. However, most of these genetic sequences have not been incorporated into the CRA's phylogeny.

CRA: “The analyses thus far performed, however, often suffer from sparse taxon sampling...”.

SA: This issue has been addressed in Liétor et al. (2025a), which compiles the findings of previous studies by Liétor's team, reporting data from more than 1,700 sampling points for genus *Iberus*.

Paragraph 3

CRA: “Recently, Liétor et al. (2024a) described three new species of *Iberus*, but these are indistinguishable and lacking any diagnostic traits”.

SA: False. While these species are largely cryptic, the cited publication (here cited as Liétor et al., 2024b) presents a long list of diagnostic criteria of various types (peristome edge, lateral bands, shell mottling, lip colour, shell surface, shell morphology, peristome shape...) summarized in a specific subhead in page 194. This matter will be revisited in greater detail later in the corresponding section.

CRA: “Liétor et al. (2024b,c,d) and Tudela et al. (2024) revise the identity and distribution of several *Iberus* from southeastern Spain, but their work includes mistakes that must be addressed...”.

SA: We will be happy to address any doubts the author may have later, one by one.

PAGE 4

Material and methods section (pages 4 and 5)

CRA presents an excessively brief and insufficiently precise Materials and methods section. It seems obvious that a much higher level of detail is required for the reader to understand the criteria employed for such a major taxonomic overhaul. In particular, the entire sampling procedure, morphological analysis, and precise taxonomic identification criteria are not explained.

Paragraph 1

CRA: “I performed my first dissection of an *Iberus* 44 years ago”.

SA: This strange phrase appears to be intended to position the author as an expert to justify his work (logical fallacy of the type *ad verecundiam*).

CRA: “Three lines of evidence have been taken into account: morphological distinctness of shells, location and length of branches”.

SA: What did CRA’s morphological study consist of? How many parameters were measured? On how many shells? Were the colors of the soft parts considered? How were the data processed? How many sampling localities were examined? What population data were collected? Was the author involved in sampling, or did they rely on data from literature or third parties? Who are these third parties, and what methodology did they follow? Is there precise traceability of the sample collection? The lack of this information can only lead one to think that this study was based on a small number of specimens, whose correct traceability has not been demonstrated. Regarding the length of the branches in a phylogenetic tree, although it represents the number of genetic changes or evolutionary time in certain models, it is not a sufficient criterion for making taxonomic decisions due to various methodological and conceptual limitations. First, the genetic divergence reflected in the length of a branch can be influenced by unequal evolutionary rates among lineages, which may create the false impression of significant taxonomic differentiation when, in reality, it is merely an acceleration in the mutation rate without a true speciation process. Additionally, factors such as genetic introgression, hybridization (very common in the genus *Iberus*), or the conservation of ancient lineages can cause species that are well-differentiated morphologically and ecologically to appear with short branches, or for populations of the same species to present long branches due to neutral processes or inadequate sampling. Furthermore, phylogenetic trees depend on the evolutionary model used and the quality of the molecular data, so biases in sequence alignment, errors in model selection, or even poor representation of the group's diversity can distort branch length estimates and lead to erroneous conclusions. Species delimitation should be based on an integrative approach that combines molecular, morphological, ecological, and biogeographical data, as only through a multidimensional evaluation is it possible to accurately determine whether a lineage truly

represents a new species or if the observed genetic divergence is an intraspecific phenomenon. In this sense, although branch length can be a useful clue within a phylogenetic analysis, it should not be the sole criterion for making taxonomic decisions, as the true nature of a species cannot be reduced solely to differences in genetic sequences without considering the evolutionary and ecological context in which it originated. For this, an exhaustive study of the territory is necessary, such as the one conducted by Liétor et al. (2025a). Despite this, CRA does not mention the methodology used to refine the branch length measurements or to compare branch lengths among species or supraspecific groups.

CRA: “In addition, a thorough revision of the nomenclatural history of this group allowed translation into a binominal classification, including the description of new subtribes, genera, subgenera, species and subspecies”.

SA: Prior to CRA’s review, Liétor et al. (2025a) provide a detailed review of the taxonomic history of all *Iberus* taxa, examining the type series and type specimens from 13 European museums and reference collections in Europe, in continuous feedback with the curators of all of them. Subsequently, some of CRA’s conclusions regarding certain taxonomic histories duplicate information already published by Liétor et al. In many other cases, the information provided by CRA regarding taxonomic histories is imprecise or leads to misinterpretations. For many of the taxa, there is a noticeable lack of in-depth analysis of the type series. After we reviewed the type series of the vast majority of *Iberus* species available in European museums, both currently accepted and synonymized, no reasons were found to justify the kind of taxonomic revolution proposed by CRA. In fact, Liétor et al. (2025a) demonstrate that, far from justifying the resurrection of certain synonyms previously discarded for the genus *Iberus*—a common practice of CRA—there is evidence to suggest that several of the type series associated with these synonymized taxa consist of mixed-species or hybrid specimens. As such, it is more appropriate to consider them invalid taxa.

Paragraph 2

CRA: “A molecular phylogeny was built using available COI sequences (Table 1)”.

SA: The sequences published in GenBank by Liétor et al. and Tudela et al. in 2024 are not included in CRA’s phylogeny, despite the references being listed in the bibliography of CRA’s review. Why does CRA not use certain freely available genetic sequences?

CRA: “COI barcoding has been proven to be an accurate tool”.

SA: The COI (cytochrome c oxidase subunit I) gene is widely used in DNA barcoding due to its high mutation rate and ease of amplification. However, it lacks the resolution necessary for accurate phylogenetic analyses (e.g., Bai et al., 2020). To obtain a more robust genetic characterization, it is strongly recommended to include nuclear genes, which provide biparental inheritance and additional genetic resolution, helping to confirm species differentiation with greater accuracy. The congruence between mitochondrial and nuclear data, along with morphological analyses, may provide robust evidence for species boundaries. Ayyagari and Sreerama (2020) provide an excellent example of this.

CRA: Making reference to COI gene: “It clearly provides a powerful basis for identification of discontinuous evolutionary groupings and species delimitation”.

SA: COI barcoding is widely used in taxonomy and biodiversity studies because mitochondrial DNA evolves relatively quickly, making COI effective for distinguishing closely related species in many animal groups. However, COI alone is not always sufficient for species delimitation due to several limitations: (i) Incomplete lineage sorting: Some species may retain ancestral COI haplotypes, making them appear more similar than they actually are; (ii) Introgression and

hybridization: Mitochondrial DNA can be transferred between species through hybridization, leading to misleading phylogenetic signals; (iii) Maternal inheritance: Because COI is inherited only through the maternal line, it does not reflect the full genetic history of a species. Nuclear genes, which are inherited from both parents, provide a more complete picture (e.g., Springer et al., 2001; Osca et al., 2014). For these reasons, while COI barcoding is a valuable starting point for species identification, it should be complemented with nuclear markers and morphological or ecological data for robust species delimitation (i.e., integrative taxonomy).

CRA: “In contrast with COI, other published short sequences (including nuclear genes) provide very limited phylogenetic information (Elejalde et al., 2008a, b; Jowers et al., 2024); although trees inferred from these other sequences agree widely with the COI tree, adding them would only increase the amount of noise over signal, and thus have not been considered”.

SA: While it is true that some short sequences, including nuclear genes, may provide limited phylogenetic information compared to more widely used markers like COI, the assertion that these sequences would “increase the amount of noise over signal” is a generalization that depends on the context. For example, short nuclear gene sequences can indeed be less informative in certain cases, especially if they lack variation or if the sample size is small. However, nuclear genes, even short ones, can still be valuable when combined with mitochondrial data, as they provide complementary information, particularly in terms of biparental inheritance, recombination, and potential for resolving phylogenetic relationships that might be unclear using COI alone. Therefore, the idea that adding these sequences would necessarily increase noise over signal may not always hold true. The integration of mitochondrial and nuclear data is commonly recommended in molecular systematics to enhance the robustness of phylogenetic conclusions. A good example of this can be found in Razkin et al. (2014). A single mitochondrial gene is not sufficient to construct a robust phylogeny and confidently conclude that a zoological group is paraphyletic. Here’s why: (i) Unique evolutionary patterns: Mitochondrial genes are maternally inherited and may be subject to selective pressures different from those affecting nuclear genes. This can lead to phylogenetic patterns that do not accurately reflect the group’s true evolutionary history; (ii) Effects of homoplasy: The relatively rapid evolution of some mitochondrial genes can result in convergences or character reversals, distorting phylogenetic relationships; (iii) Possible introgression or hybridization: The transfer of mitochondrial genes between species through hybridization events can obscure the true evolutionary history of the group. Liétor et al. (2025a) provide strong evidence that hybridization is a highly frequent phenomenon in the genus *Iberus*. In fact, CRA’s approach to his whole study and all his argument contradicts contemporary phylogenetic knowledge as well as the whole field of phylogenomics.

Paragraph 3

CRA “Sequences were aligned with MUSCLE and the resulting alignment was curated with Gblocks”.

SA: Gblocks can help exclude poorly aligned positions and divergent regions of an alignment. This software is particularly useful for highly divergent sequence data such as rRNA sequences for example, where multiple indels or gaps are problematic to infer homology. Nevertheless, the COI gene fragment is a protein coding gene and therefore lacks indels and shows no highly divergent regions. Upon inspection, the nucleotide alignment and its translation into amino acids showed uninterrupted reading frames, no premature stop codons, and no evidence of hypervariable regions. Thus using GBlocks is unnecessary and should not be used as any deleted regions would affect and topology. In addition, CRA does not mention what regions were excluded from analysis nor what settings were used in GBlocks, details which are highly important as they change the alignment, the core of the study.

CRA: “Branch support was calculated as SH-like aLRT after 100 bootstraps”.

SA: Where are the branch supports and why are they not shown? What is the point of arguing about the importance of them if CRA then does not use them as evidence?.

Paragraph 4

CRA: “All algorithms devised for phylogenetic inference are prone to artifacts, often unavoidable. In particular, long-branch attraction is of special concern when branch lengths differ widely, a common situation when taxon sampling is uneven and insufficient; it is also a real threat when there is across-site compositional heterogeneity, even when data are partitioned. In order to detect and avoid such artifacts, numerous trees were inferred, adding taxa stepwise and controlling for any topological changes, until a stable pattern remained”.

SA: CRA does not mention if he actually found any lineages with long branches. We encountered none within the ingroup. To what artifacts does he refer to? What does a stable pattern mean? This is really not an optimal strategy as it prevents repeatability. This explanation and method are highly subjective and unscientific. A published article needs all details and parameters used for others to repeat if needed. What is a stable pattern anyways? Is this not measured by bootstrap support?

Paragraph 5

CRA: “Delimitation of species has been performed taking into account three lines of evidence: morphological distinctiveness, appreciable genetic differentiation, and biogeographic separation”.

SA: How did CRA do it? CRA does not specify any methodology approach in this regard.

PAGE 5

Paragraph 1

CRA: “The new species and subspecies are identifiable on the basis of shell characters that appear to be diagnostic and unequivocal”.

SA: Later on, we will review many cases in which CRA uses characters subject to notable intraspecific or even intrapopulational variability, as revealed by Liétor et al. (2025a), to define new taxa. These are highly ambiguous characters, never "unequivocal".

CRA: “Anatomical data and the resulting phylogenetic analyses are in progress.”

SA: This is quite confusing. Does that mean that the anatomical results do not change the phylogeny and the taxonomic decisions presented here in any way? Then, what added value are they supposed to provide?

CRA: “The new material on which this study is based has been deposited in the author’s Museographic Collection (CRA)”.

SA: There is no article in the ICZN that explicitly determines in which type of institutions the type specimens of a new species should be deposited. However, there are some recommendations regarding this:

(i) Recommendation 16C. Preservation and deposition of type specimens. Recognizing that name-bearing types are international standards of reference (see Article 72.10) authors should deposit type specimens in an institution that maintains a research collection, with proper

facilities for preserving them and making them accessible for study (i.e. one which meets the criteria in Recommendation 72F).

(ii) Recommendation 72F.1 ensure that all are clearly marked so that they will be unmistakably recognized as name-bearing types; 72F.2 take all necessary steps for their safe preservation; 72F.3 make them accessible for study; 72F.4 publish lists of name-bearing types in its possession or custody; and 72F.5 so far as possible, communicate information concerning name-bearing types when requested.

On August 27, 2024, a researcher collaborating with us sent the following email to CRA, requesting information about *Tartessiberus cilbanus*:

“De: We prefer to keep the sender anonymous

Fecha: El mar, 27 ago 2024 a las 0:41

Asunto: Holotipo de *Tartessiberus cilbanus*

Para: email provided by CRA in its publications, including Altaba and Ríos Jiménez (2021)

Estimado Sr.:

Me pongo en contacto con usted para solicitar fotografías del holotipo de *Tartessiberus cilbanus* que, según el artículo donde se publica la especie, obra en su poder. Muchas gracias por adelantado.

Atentamente; The sender”

No response was ever received.

It is true that a photograph of this holotype appears in the original publication of the species, but it is also true that Liétor et al. (2025a) have identified cases in which a holotype photograph published in a scientific journal does not match the image provided by the museum housing the specimen. Throughout our research, we consistently took care to verify the correspondence between the actual holotypes (physical shells) and the published photographs. This case was no exception.

Our inability to verify the existence and access the information of the holotype of *Tartessiberus cilbanus*, not deposited in the zoological collection of an institution, contravenes recommendations 72F.3 and 72F.5 of the ICZN. However, had its existence been verified, would the information from this source be reliable, or would it be compromised in light of recommendation 72F.1 of the Code?

It seems logical that a specimen, which will indefinitely represent a species, should remain housed in a permanent institution whose continuity over time is guaranteed and whose cataloging and management procedures are governed by standardized methods.

Moreover, CRA states in his original publication (Altaba and Ríos Jiménez, 2021), also in *Folia Conchylologica*, that paratype 2 of *Tartessiberus cilbanus* is deposited in the Balearic Natural Sciences Museum. This was the response of the Conservator of the mentioned Museum to the information request from J. Liétor, dated August 5, 2024.

Estimado José,

Desconocía este artículo y el hecho de que se tuvieran que depositar muestras en nuestro museo. El autor en ningún caso me informó de ello y no ha traído ninguna muestra para su depósito. Quizás puede mirar de contactar con él directamente.

Lamento no poder ayudarle.

Un saludo,

Translated to English with Google Translate: “Dear José, I was unaware of this article and the fact that samples had to be deposited at our museum. The author [CRA] never informed me of this and hasn't brought any samples for deposit. Perhaps you could try contacting him directly. I'm sorry I can't help you. Regards,”

Throughout his review, CRA invokes the ICZN to justify numerous criticisms, yet disregards its principles in his own taxonomic practice.

It is worrying that the specimens used to describe the holotypes and paratypes described by CRA are not accessible to other researchers, but even more worrying is that CRA states in its publications that they are deposited in an institution where they are not in fact.

Paragraph 3

CRA: “The geographical distribution of species-level taxa is shown in maps, without extensive locality data”.

SA: The maps at the end of the article only show clouds without specific sampling points. How were these clouds delineated? How many sampling points were used to define them? Were the data obtained firsthand, from the literature, or a mix of both? If literature data were used, from what date were they considered? Many citations from the literature are erroneous, outdated, or simply refer to locations where there is now an urbanization, a cultivated field, or a burned forest, but no snails. Was the critical issue of hybridization taken into account?

CRA: “A more thorough monograph is in preparation. The goal of this paper is to establish the framework for a much more extensive treatment of the Allognathini”.

SA: It does not seem appropriate that, under the justification of a later, more extensive publication, many of the methodological aspects and field data that CRA apparently has are withheld from this “overarching” publication.

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Paragraph 6

CRA: “Its inclusion as a sister group to other Allognathini by Neiber et al. (2022) is probably an artifact of long-branch attraction, likely caused by insufficient taxonomic coverage and aggravated by partitioning”.

SA: Neiber et al. (2021) actually used PartitionFinder and partition by codon for protein codon genes, a this is a known way to solve possible long-branch attraction. This was also employed in Liétor et al. (2024a-c, g, 2025b), Jowers et al. (2024) and Tudela et al. (2024). Interestingly, it seems that CRA never employed partition by codon to avoid this issue, this is intriguing as he seems to be most concerned by long-branch attraction and he did nothing to avoid it.

Paragraph 8

CRA: “The earliest offshoot within the Allognathini is the monotypic *Pseudotachea*. The position of *Helix liturata* Pfeiffer, 1853 (until now placed in *Pseudotachea*) as a second basal lineage would make this genus paraphyletic, so a new genus is proposed for it”.

SA: Not only CRA changes *Pseudotachea* to a new subtribe based on only one sample and one COI sequence but he also creates a subtribe for it (*Pseudotacheina*). To make matters worse he names another new genus for *Pseudotachea* (*Herculiberus*) and once more based on one specimen he creates a new subtribe for it (*Herculiberina*). We are intrigued to know what CRA thinks a genus and a subtribe are as there seems to be no clear explanation to his reclassification. This wrong doing applies to most groups in his paper, a continuous taxonomical splitting of taxa.

Paragraph 10

CRA: "In these new areas it hybridizes with native *Iberus*, but the viability of those hybrids and the possible resulting introgression remain to be assessed".

SA: The work of Liétor et al. (2025a) provides overwhelming evidence on the issue of hybridization, including multiple breeding experiences involving hybrid crosses.

Paragraph 11

CRA: "*I. latissimus* spec. nov. is found in the range's southwestern slopes. *I. mariae* lives only in the near-insular tip of Punta Entinas further south; its small size may be interpreted as a case of island dwarfism".

SA: On what argumentation is that conclusion based? CRA acknowledges that the *I. mariae* confined to the coastal cliffs of Punta Entinas is a case of local dwarfism. So why does he arbitrarily define *I. latissimus*, which, according to Liétor et al. (2024e), corresponds to a larger interior form? CRA contradicts itself in this statement and, inadvertently, agrees with us.

Paragraph 1

CRA: "In order to render *Helix obversa* Born, 1778 an objective junior synonym of *H. gualtierana*, I hereby designate as lectotype of *H. obversa* the same specimen depicted by Gualtieri".

SA: The holotype of *H. obversa* (location of unknown origin) remains deposited in the Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Austria, with reference NHMW-MO-14817 (see photo in Liétor et al., 2025a, p. 242). Therefore, no lectotype is required.

Paragraph 5

CRA: "Liétor et al. (2024c) rank *I. (I.) ornatissimus* as a subspecies of *I. mariae* and describe a "new form" from the southwestern sector of Sierra de Gádor on the basis of linear shell measurements and the unsubstantiated hypothesis of widespread hybridization in large contact areas. *Iberus mariae mariae* f. *macrolabiatus* Liétor, Tudela, Jódar, Galán-Luque & Jowers, 2024 is an infrasubspecific name proposed with no type; thus it is unavailable."

SA: This paragraph is filled with inaccuracies. CRA misrepresents several ideas from Liétor et al. (2024e), taking them out of context and linking them in an arbitrary manner. Let's clarify them one by one: (i) Liétor et al. (2024e) also provide detailed evidence on the geographic distribution of congeneric taxa, along with genetic data, for the mentioned taxon. (ii) Hybridization is not considered a taxonomic argument in Liétor et al. (2024e), who instead regard this taxon as a peculiar form of *I. mariae mariae*, occurring in an area where extensive hybridization with other congeneric taxa occurs. (iii) The phrase "an infrasubspecific name proposed with no type; thus it is unavailable" is unclear to us. If we understand correctly, what CRA is trying to convey is that the lack of a type specimen invalidates the *macrolabiatus* form described by Liétor et al. Article 72.8 of the ICZN stipulates that a nominal species and its nominotypical subspecies share the same name-bearing type. This means that the specimen designated as the type for the main species (nominal species) also serves as the type for its nominotypical subspecies. In addition, an infrasubspecies does not require a type designation according to the ICZN. While Liétor et al. (2024e) present substantial evidence suggesting that this taxon is an ecotype of *I. mariae mariae*, CRA arbitrarily creates a new species without providing any data, beyond a vague description of the shell. Liétor et al. conducted numerous samplings in the area of this taxon (currently accepted as *I. mariae mariae* f. *macrolabiatus*) and found no evidence to suggest that

it could even be considered a new subspecies (much less a new species), despite its morphological traits that differ from the nominal species.

Paragraph 9

CRA: "Type material. - Spain, Andalucía, Almería province, Poniente Almeriense county, Dalías, 36° 48' N, 2° 51' W".

SA: These coordinates, according to Liétor et al. (2025a, Annex 1), correspond to the area where hybrid populations of *I. mariae mariae* f. *macrolabiatus* and *I. rhodopeplus bastetanus* are found. To locate pure populations of *I. mariae mariae* f. *macrolabiatus*, one must move 4 km west. It therefore seems that CRA intends to define a new species based on potentially hybrid specimens.

Paragraph 10

CRA: "*Iberus (I.) latissimus* spec. nov. is distributed over the southwestern slopes of the Sierra de Gádor (Fig. 3)".

SA: This CRA's new taxon does not appear in the phylogenetic tree (Figure 1 in CRA's paper) due to the lack of available genetic data. This highlights that the author's primary criterion for defining new taxa throughout this study relies on uncertain and highly variable morphological characters.

Paragraph 14

CRA: "The color pattern of *I. (I.) latissimus* is similar to that of *I. (I.) ornatissimus*".

SA: Perhaps specific specimens could be found that may show some similarity between both taxa, but the truth is that both the color and ornamentations of shells are distinct (Figure 2). See additional shell images in Annex 2 of Liétor et al. (2025a).

Figure 2. Representative shells of *I. mariae mariae* f. *macrolabiatus* (*I. (I.) latissimus* according to CRA) from Alcaudique, Berja, Almería, 34 mm (left) and *I. mariae ornatissimus* (*I. (I.) ornatissimus* according to CRA) from Alhama de Almería, Almería, 32 mm (right).

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Paragraph 5

CRA: "*Iberus (Labioiberus) campesinus lorcanus* (Rossmässler, 1854) is considered a valid subspecies".

SA: This is not true (see [Molluscabase](#)). Liétor et al. (2025a) show that, although two subgroups appear to emerge within the *I. campesinus* lineage, the genetic distances are insufficient to define subspecies.

Paragraph 8

CRA: "There is, however, a phylogeographic structure, which supports the recognition of parapatric subspecies".

SA: Which phylogeographic structure? The author arbitrarily defines subspecies without providing any solid justification. Nor does he review the taxonomic status of the taxon named *lorcanus*; he simply asserts that it is a valid taxon, which is wrong (see Liétor et al., 2025a).

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Paragraph 3

CRA: "The localities plotted by Liétor et al. (2024d) near the coast may be in part due to confusion with *I. (Carthaginiberus) carthaginiensis posthumus*"

SA: Incorrect. *Iberus gualtieranus posthumus* is a synonym of *I. alonensis*, as explicitly stated in Liétor et al. (2025a). The holotype and the extensive series of paratypes of *I. gualtieranus posthumus* are deposited in the Naturmuseum Senckenberg in Frankfurt. Liétor et al. (2025a), reported that the original material used to define this taxon corresponds to a mixture of *I. campesinus* f. *lorcanus* and hybrid forms of this with *I. carthaginiensis*.

Paragraph 4

CRA: "*Helix pseudo-campesina* Kobelt, 1910 is based on a specimen collected by Pallary. The locality of Los Millares given by Kobelt (1910) is an obvious mistake, as it was surely found at Pozo del Esparto, at the easternmost tip of Andalusia."

SA: If it is stated that it is an "obvious mistake," it is necessary to explain why. Otherwise, these are mere assumptions. No type specimens are provided, nor is there any morphological comparison with the supposedly correct species. Liétor et al. (2025a) analyze this matter in greater detail, showing images of the holotype and paratype of *Helix alonensis pseudocampesina* Kobelt, 1909, deposited in the Naturmuseum Senckenberg in Frankfurt.

Paragraph 9

CRA: In reference to *Iberus (Labioiberus) campesinus bastetanus* subsp. nov.: "Type material. - Spain, Murcia region and province, Alto Guadalentín county, Lorca, Sierra de La Carrasquilla, 37° 34' N; 1° 34' W, ca. 650 m, under esparto grasses; 23.i.2015, J. Liétor col. Holotype."

SA: As the collector of the holotype, J. Liétor is thoroughly familiar with this population and confirms that it is a specimen of *I. campesinus* f. *lorcanus*. Indeed, morphologically, this taxon (pictured in Fig. 5 in CRA's paper) exhibits the typical traits of *I. campesinus* f. *lorcanus* (see Liétor et al., 2025a, especially Annex 2). CRA insists on defining taxa that fall within the well-documented range of variability for the species, which highlights a misunderstanding of the conchological variation within the genus *Iberus*. In any case, even if this taxon is not valid, the subspecific designation "*bastetanus*" has been already used by Liétor et al. (2025b) to refer to *Iberus rhodopeplus bastetanus*.

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Paragraph 2

CRA: "*Iberus (L.) campesinus bastetanus* subsp. nov. occurs at the northeastern limit of the species range. Between *I. (L.) c. campesinus* and the new subspecies, *I. (L.) c. lorcanus* is intermediate morphologically and geographically.

SA: Liétor et al. (2025a) were able, only after a comprehensive long-term study, to unravel the numerous contact zones between *Iberus* taxa and the potential 38 hybrid forms within the genus. *Iberus campesinus* f. *lorcanus* hybridizes with *I. xerophilus*, *I. rhodopeplus*, *I. carthaginiensis*, and *I. gualtieranus*. The intermediate specimens referred to by CRA could very well correspond to some of these hybrids. What do intermediate forms mean for CRA? Do they have any impact on their taxonomic decisions? It seems not. CRA has no excuse for being unaware of hybridization. For example, Jowers et al. (2024) and Liétor et al. (2024d), both cited in CRA's reference list, highlighted the intense hybridization processes occurring within the genus *Iberus*.

Paragraph 9

CRA: "The two species in *Iberus* (*Carthaginiberus*) have been treated as subspecies (Elejalde et al., 2008b; Bank & Luijten, 2015), but they are morphologically distinct. *I. (C.) bajoi* is definitely larger, and has the last whorl more inflated below and less expanded near the aperture".

SA: This statement lacks any morphometric support; it is an assessment presumably based on variable traits and the observation of few specimens. According to Liétor et al. (2025a), *Helix bajoi* is a synonym of *I. alonensis*.

CRA: "In spite of moderate genetic differentiation, they are best treated as allopatric species".

SA: What does moderate genetic differentiation mean? In what magnitude and units is it measured? Moderate in relation to what?

Paragraph 11

CRA: Making reference to *I. carthaginiensis*: "Although there are no DNA sequences available for this taxon, the shells suggest it is closely related to the type species of the subgenus. It differs in having a more expanded aperture and a more reflected peristome".

SA: COI sequences from 4 specimens of *I. carthaginiensis* were published by Tudela et al. (2024), a reference that is included in CRA's review. Although these sequences have not yet been released due to reasons unrelated to the authors (probably due to a lack of synchronization between the journal and GenBank), CRA could have requested these sequences from the authors or facilitated their release on GenBank. It would be worth asking the author why he chose not to access this information, just as he chose not to use many of the other COI sequences from previous publications by Liétor et al., which are available on GenBank. Anyway, CRA continues to base his taxonomic decisions on variable conchological characters, neglecting the ecological pressures that shape shell morphology or the morphological sequence observed in *I. carthaginiensis* in the southeastern Iberian Peninsula (Murcia region), particularly in response to hybridization with *I. punicus* (see Tudela et al., 2024 and Liétor et al., 2025a).

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Paragraph 4

CRA: "A further level of noise has recently been introduced by Tudela et al. (2024), who for some reason think the name *I. carthaginiensis* should apply to specimens that do not fit the original description (and illustration), nor live anywhere near the type locality".

SA: What CRA states in this paragraph is incorrect. It is surprising that CRA dismisses such a complex paper as that of Tudela et al. (2024) with expressions like "further level of noise" and "for some reason". Indeed, in Tudela et al. (2024), the authors provide a solid set of valid reasons to support the taxonomic decisions made. CRA distorts and oversimplifies the authors' arguments to suit his own interests, which is unacceptable. In Tudela et al. (2024), the opposite of what CRA claims occurs: The populations attributed by Tudela et al. to *I. carthaginiensis* are

those that were classically attributed to this taxon (before *I. calaensis* was incorrectly described). See Tudela et al. (2024) for further details.

CRA: “Thus, they describe the eastern set of populations (including the area around Cartagena) as the alleged new species *Iberus punicus* Tudela, Liétor, Jódar, Galán-Luque & Jowers, 2024. This is clearly a junior (subjective) synonym of *Helix carthaginiensis* Rossmässler, 1853. What they assume should bear Rossmässler’s name is unequivocally *I. (C.) carthaginiensis posthumus* Haas, 1934”.

SA: Another list of claims without supporting arguments. On the one hand, in the study by Tudela et al. (2024), a phylogenetic tree is constructed based on 3 genes, in which all the samples of the former *I. carthaginiensis* taken east of Cartagena formed a new clade, which had gone unnoticed until then, with strong support and high genetic distances for COI and 16S rRNA compared to *I. carthaginiensis*. If we add to that the geographical separation, the morphometric study of 788 shells, and the differences in conchological patterns and even in foot coloration (see also Liétor et al., 2025a), the evidence to describe *I. punicus* is conclusive. On the other hand, after examining the type series from the Naturmuseum Senckenberg in Frankfurt, Liétor et al. (2025a) demonstrated that the original material used to define *I. gualtieranus posthumus* corresponds to a mix of *I. campesinus* f. *lorcanus* and hybrid forms of this with *I. carthaginiensis*. Since the type series is compromised, the name *posthumus* must be invalidated.

CRA: “Tudela et al. (2024) acknowledge there are specimens with intermediate morphology at the limit between the two taxa. They interpret this as evidence of introgression between two distinct species. However, it seems more parsimonious to consider such individuals as belonging to a narrow zone of contact between neighboring subspecies”.

SA: The expression "it seems..." is not appropriate in a scientific context, unless solid arguments are provided to support it. Otherwise, it may be interpreted as an unfounded opinion of CRA. Arbitrarily defining species in the absence of solid morphological or genetic evidence, as CRA does, particularly in regions lacking geographical barriers that would justify such distinctions, is scientifically unsound. We recommend that CRA carefully review the sections on hybridization in Liétor et al. (2025a), including the multiple hybrid breeding experiments conducted in captivity by the authors.

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Paragraph 3

CRA: “However, Bourguignat’s description unequivocally points at a species of *Iberus (Carthaginiberus)* with depressed spire, last whorl inflated below, and relatively large size. The single specimen of *H. bajoi* in the Bourguignat collection, housed at the Muséum d’Histoire naturelle in Geneva (Switzerland) is a syntype corresponding entirely with the original description; it is most likely that the description was based on this particular and only specimen”.

SA: Proposing to revive a taxonomic name based on a single specimen with uncertain traceability, relying on a conchological description that could apply to multiple *Iberus* forms, and overlooking the extensive hybridization zone in the studied area is scientifically questionable. In Liétor et al. (2025a), several cases are reported in which type series deposited in certain museums were found to be mixtures of different species, sometimes also mixed with hybrids. The case of *I. loxanus* is particularly striking. Similarly, we demonstrate the numerous errors in the traceability of the classical naturalists involved in the early taxonomy of the genus *Iberus*. In fact, the research by Liétor et al. (2025a) helped clarify many museum records related to these type series. Therefore, any taxonomic decision made regarding these old type series should be approached with skepticism and caution.

CRA: “Thus, the specimen with catalogue number MHNG-MOLL-118673 (Fig. 6) is hereby designated as lectotype of *Helix bajoi* Bourguignat in Servain, 1881”.

SA: The specimens illustrated in Figs. 6-8 in CRA paper (including the holotype for *I. bajoi* in Fig. 6) show conchological traits attributable to hybrids between *I. globulosus* and *I. rhodopeplus bastetanus* (see Liétor et al., 2025a, including Annexes 1 and 2). In Liétor et al. (2024d), it is shown that the geographical location of the specimen in Fig. 6 falls within an extensive area of hybrids.

Paragraph 5

CRA: “Boettger (1913) interpreted the different shell morphologies as indicating a gradual transition encompassing all *Iberus*; as an extreme form of this apparent continuum, he introduced *I. gualtieranus globulosus* Boettger, 1913 (the species name was misspelled as *gualterianus*). Such interpretation was based on questionable conchological and taxonomic criteria, and is not supported by the results of the present study”.

SA: CRA considers the conchological diagnostic criteria of other authors as questionable, while his own appears infallible. When it states "is not supported by the results of the present study" what exactly is being referred to?

Paragraph 6

CRA: “Liétor et al. (2024d) propose a neotype designation for *Iberus gualtieranus globulosus*. However, the qualifying conditions of Art. 75.3 did not apply, as there was no exceptional need to designate a neotype. As stated by Zilch (1977), the holotype was destroyed during World War II. However, it is unequivocally identifiable in the work by Boettger (1913: p. 196, fig. 8), who clearly states that it comes from around Almería. This must mean the province of Almería, as he only provides this level of geographical precision for other taxa he mentions. The only part of the Almería province where *Iberus bajoi* (= *globulosus*) lives is Los Vélez county, the northernmost district; this area belongs to the eastwards flowing Segura drainage, in contrast with the rest of the province. Although this is a mountain region, it is crossed by the main road connecting Murcia and Granada, so collecting there was easy over a century ago. Furthermore, there is an appreciable variation in shell features across the species range; Boettger’s specimen matches those from Almería province, and differs from those living further north and northeast. However, Liétor et al (2024d) state: “the neotype of *I. globulosus* does not completely match the shell characters and the locality of the morphotype originally assigned to the species”. Although it seems normal that a shell cannot match completely another shell, so deviating a little from the original would certainly not invalidate a neotype designation, shells were available that would match much better the original; this is in violation of Art. 75.3.5. They also state: “It may seem unorthodox to assign a neotype having a location different from the original type locality”. This is a more serious issue, as specimens collected in the area given as type locality were available to the authors; this is in violation of Art. 75.3.6. Both statements show theirs is an invalid neotype designation, as it is clearly and admittedly contrary to Article 75 of the Code, which mandates that a neotype must be consistent with what is known of the former name-bearing type from the original description (Art. 75.3.5), as well as that it must come from as nearly as practicable from the original type locality (Art. 75.3.6)”.

SA: Almería has an area of nearly 9,000 km²; therefore, it cannot be an unequivocal type locality, but rather the opposite. The variation the author mentions in the conchological traits is what one would expect in an area of intense hybridization, probably the most complex in all of Andalusia (see Liétor et al., 2024d). The author's claim that *I. bajoi* inhabits only the Los Vélez area in the province of Almería, without a study of the surrounding *Iberus* populations, appears unfounded. Once again, a species is described by CRA as being restricted to a limited area

without clear geographic barriers, relying solely on conchological traits (despite the genus *Iberus* being known for its cryptic species) without providing robust supporting evidence. The classification appears to be based primarily on the author's subjective assessment. The most serious aspect of this paragraph is that CRA engages in a rather crude and unethical misrepresentation of the available scientific data since he selectively excerpts passages from Liétor et al.'s article while omitting key arguments that clarify the rationale for changing the type locality. To preserve the integrity of the original text, we refrain from rewriting it here and instead encourage readers to consult Liétor et al. (2024d) directly.

Paragraph 7

CRA: "A useful neotype designation is proposed herein in order to clarify and stabilize the identity and type locality of this nominal taxon, thus preventing any further arbitrary changes".

SA: What Liétor et al. (2024d) intended was precisely to avoid selecting a neotype from a location where an intense hybridization process between *I. globulosus* and *I. rhodopeplus bastetanus* occurs. The morphological traits of the neotype shown by CRA in his Fig. 7 and 8 leave no doubt that this specimen is a hybrid form (see Liétor et al., 2025a). Indeed, the unequivocal proof of the hybrid character is provided by Fig. 7, where we observe a pinkish mantle, a trait contributed by *I. rhodopeplus bastetanus* while *I. globulosus* has a whitish mantle (see page 188 and Annex 2 of Liétor et al., 2025a).

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Paragraph 9

CRA: Making reference to new taxa within *Iberus* (*Nazariberus*) subgen. nov.- "*Iberus* (*Nazariberus*) *rhodopeplus* Aguilar-Amat, 1925, *I. (N.) labiatus* Ahuir Galindo, 1989, *I. (N.) turdetanus* sp. nov., and *I. (N.) selambinicus* sp. nov".

SA: In Liétor et al. (2025b), solid evidence to invalidate the taxonomic denomination *I. alonensis labiatus* is provided.

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Paragraph 3

CRA: "For unclear reasons, Liétor et al. (2024 b) decided to explicitly dismiss the description of *I. rhodopeplus* by Aguilar-Amat (1925), and describe *Iberus sumuntanus* Liétor, Tudela & Jódar, 2024 from a site located just 5 km northeast of the former's type locality. The only diagnostic traits on which *I. sumuntanus* is based are average measurements of eight specimens (smaller average shell diameter, lower average shell height, and smaller average associated measurements); however, the small type series exhibits a wide variation in size and shape, making it impossible to allocate an individual into this nominal species. The morphological record strongly suggests that *I. sumuntanus* is a junior (subjective) synonym of *Iberus rhodopeplus* Aguilar- Amat, 1925".

SA: CRA claims that only 8 shells were measured, which is false. All the shells found at 8 sampling locations were measured, totalling 478, as clearly stated in Table 2 of Liétor et al. (2024f). Once again, the author is mistaken in claiming that Liétor et al. use only 3 morphometric parameters when, in fact, we employed up to 11 (Table 2 of the same article). There are very few studies on terrestrial gastropods that reach such a high number of measured shells, making this even more significant given that the species has an estimated distribution area of just 6 km². Indeed, *I. rhodopeplus* from Cerro Morocho is close to *I. sumuntanus* from Pegalajar, exactly about 5 km away in a straight line. Should this be a problem, considering that *I. sumuntanus* has such a restricted distribution? Clearly not. Additionally, *I. sumuntanus* is one of the most well-

characterized *Iberus* species both morphologically and geographically (Liétor et al., 2024f). We invite the readers to verify this by consulting pages 290–297 in Liétor et al. (2025a). The type series of *I. sumuntanus* consists of a holotype and 8 paratypes, conchologically contrasted (Plate 1 of the aforementioned article). This is more than a representative sample for a species with such a limited distribution. Moreover, some of these specimens are preserved in two museum institutions, including the National Museum of Natural Sciences (Madrid, Spain). Paratypes of a new species are carefully selected to capture the broadest possible variability not represented by the holotype. Therefore, CRA's statement "It is impossible to allocate an individual into this nominal species," is perplexing. In fact, Liétor et al. had no difficulty selecting the ecotype assigned to the holotype, as their comprehensive understanding of the species enabled them to identify the most common and, consequently, the most representative ecotype.

Paragraph 4

CRA: "In order to identify the unique bearer of the name of a nominal species-group taxon and the standard for its application (Art. 74.1), the syntype from the type series of *Iberus alonensis rhodopeplus* Aguilar-Amat, 1925 with catalogue number MZB-89-2580 in the Museu de Ciències Naturals de Barcelona, and measuring 36.2 mm in maximum diameter, is herein designated as lectotype (Fig. 9)".

SA: Indeed, this is the same conclusion previously reached by Liétor et al. (2025a; p. 278), so it does not represent a novel contribution.

Paragraph 6

CRA: "The description of *Iberus labiatus* Ahuir Galindo, 1989 is sufficient to consider it a distinct taxon".

SA: The description by Ahuir Galindo (in 2026, not 1989) lacks genetic analysis and is based on weak conchological traits measured from a limited sample of shells, leading Liétor et al. (2025b) to consider it a synonym of *I. rhodopeplus rhodopeplus* Aguilar-Amat, 1925.

Paragraph 8

CRA: "Diagnosis. - Differs from *I. (N.) rhodopeplus* in having a heavier, white peristome with a more reflected lip, and a thicker shell. It lacks the conspicuously expanded last quarter whorl of *I. (N.) selambinicus* and *I. (N.) labiatus*, as well as the expanded peristome of the latter. The shell is usually very pale".

SA: Building on the author's earlier analogy (for *I. sumuntanus*) that measuring only a few shells is insufficient to characterize a species, in this case, the author proceeds without measuring any shells and fails to provide geographic or morphological data at the metapopulation level. This suggests that CRA's description may be potentially based on a single or few shells. It is important to remember that the *I. rhodopeplus* complex contains cryptic taxa (Liétor et al., 2025b). For this reason, several reviewers of Liétor et al. (2025b) did not accept that, despite the two lineages identified by the authors showing a genetic divergence of 9.54% for COI and 4.82% for 16S rRNA, they could not be defined as distinct species due to their indistinguishable shells. As a result, they had to be classified within the subspecies range.

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Paragraph 1

CRA: Making reference to *Iberus (Nazariberus) turdetanus* spec. nov.- "La Mella mountain, 37° 45'3 N, 3° 49' W, ca. 1100 m, in limestone crevices covered by Mediterranean shrubs; 8.i.2013, J. Liétor, col. Holotype".

SA: The collector of the holotype (J. Liétor) states that there are no reasons to consider that shell or its population of origin as a taxon different from *I. rhodopeplus rhodopeplus*.

Paragraph 8

CRA: Making reference to *Iberus (Nazariberus) selambinicus* spec. nov.- “Differs from *I. (N.) labiatus* in lacking an expanded, flaring peristome. It is distinguished from both *I. (N.) turdetanus* and *I. (N.) rhodopeplus* by its bulging, more expanded last quarter whorl”.

SA: We invite the readers to review Annex 2 of Liétor et al. (2025a) to observe the degree of variability exhibited by the shells of *Iberus* species. Even more importantly, we urge them to understand how the frequent hybridization between neighboring congeneric taxa results in intermediate shells —shells that could easily be used to describe new species if one lacks a thorough understanding of distributions and interspecific contact zones. CRA treats subtle and variable conchological traits as if they were exclusive to certain taxa, making them easily distinguishable from others, but that is not how it works. Conchological traits vary tremendously between populations and sometimes even within the same population. One might assume that a slightly thickened lip is characteristic of population A, until specimens with the same trait are discovered in population B, located far from population A. Therefore, we must emphasize that conchological traits are only useful when analyzed across a large number of shells at a metapopulation scale and within the framework of a multidisciplinary approach that includes a deep understanding of distribution and genetics.

Paragraph 9

CRA: Making reference to *Iberus (Nazariberus) selambinicus* spec. nov.- “Description.- Shell dextral, very large, moderately thick, semiglobose...”.

SA: It would be worth asking CRA whether this conchological description is based solely on the specimens provided by J. Liétor, or if he has visited the specific location in Granada to sample additional specimens and verify their average morphometric parameters. If not, his description is based on a very limited number of specimens—specifically, according to J. Liétor's records, only two specimens sent to CRA by him in December 2015.

Paragraph 10

CRA: Making reference to *Iberus (Nazariberus) selambinicus* spec. nov.- “Spain, Andalucía, Granada province, Costa Granadina county, Salobreña, Tajo de la Virgen, 36° 47' N 3° 32' W, ca.120 m, under esparto grasses; 21.x.2015, J. Liétor, col. Holotype”.

SA: The type locality mentioned here corresponds to the species *I. rhodopeplus rhodopeplus*, which is well characterized by Liétor et al. (2025b). As declared by CRA, the specimens from his unnecessary type locality are, on average, larger than those from other surrounding mountain ranges, but there is nothing particularly noteworthy about this: it is merely intraspecific variability.

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Paragraph 2

CRA: “Unfortunately, the original description of *Helix alonensis* suffers from two major shortcomings. First, none of the five varieties was designated as typical. It is now clear that at least two different species were included in the original description: one is represented by varieties 1 to 4 (alpha to delta) have no conspicuous banding and come from the València region (Alacant and València), and the other, much larger variety 5 (epsilon), exhibits well-defined bands and lives in Andalusia (Almería). Later authors remarked that the former has always a grey mantle, whilst the latter has a purplish red mantle when adult”.

SA: CRA is confusing the Epsilon form of the original *Helix alonensis* with the current *I. rhodopeplus* ssp. The Epsilon form of CRA's *H. alonensis*, currently accepted as *I. xerophilus* (Liétor et al., 2024a), has a white mantle (see page 188 and Annex 2 in Liétor et al., 2025a). The pink or salmon-colored mantle (not typically as intense as purplish red) is characteristic of *I. rhodopeplus* ssp. (see Liétor et al., 2025a,b). In addition, *I. rhodopeplus* ssp. does not overlap geographically with *I. xerophilus*. It seems that the author is unfamiliar with both the morphology and the distribution of these species. For more information on the complex taxonomic history of *I. alonensis* and the misinterpretations by García San Nicolás (1957) mentioned by CRA, we suggest consulting Liétor et al. (2025a, pp. 189–196).

Paragraph 3

CRA: “In fact, Férussac’s opinion was quite the contrary, as variety 5 from Almería was deemed to be “the type” shortly after the species description, as attested by the following three sentences (Férussac & Deshayes, 1820-1851a: 121): “Nous avons une petit variété qui n’est guère plus grande que notre *Helix nemoralis*, le type de l’espèce acquiert le triple ce volume” [We have a small variety that is barely larger than our *Helix [Cepaea] nemoralis*, the type of the species acquires a volume triple than this]; “Mais dans le type de l’espèce, il existe constamment quatre ou cinq zone brunes dont les deux inférieures sont toujours plus nettes et plus foncées que les trois autres” [But in the type of the species, there exist constantly four or five brown zones, the lower two being always more neatly defined and darker than the other three]: “Le manteau est d’un beau rose légèrement purpurin” [The mantle is of a beautiful, slightly purplish rose]. It is thus clear that the intention was to restrict the “type” to variety 5”.

SA: CRA's review is yet another example of the tremendous confusion surrounding the taxonomic classification of all the large, globose *Iberus* taxa from the southeastern Iberian Peninsula, traditionally grouped under the "*alonensis*" morphotype. Liétor et al. (2025a) provided numerous pieces of evidence that reorder the classic *I. alonensis* into several species, including *I. xerophilus* (provisionally referred to as *I. alonensis*-like 01 by Elejalde et al., 2008b). Let's review the three ideas CRA used to define his new *I. alonensis* (currently *I. xerophilus*), all of which are underlined in the previous paragraph: (i) It is wrong that the Epsilon form of *H. alonensis* is larger. According to the data from Liétor et al. (2025a), *I. xerophilus* has an average diameter of 31.2 mm (n=624) compared to the average diameter of 29.3 mm for *I. alonensis* (n=757); the former is certainly not three times the size of the latter. (ii) The statement assigned to the type specimen of the species—"there exist constantly four or five brown zones, the lower two being always more neatly defined and darker than the other three"—is applicable to the Alicante and Levante region populations of the current *I. alonensis* if we interpret zones as lines/bands (see Annex 2 of Liétor et al., 2025a). (iii) Most importantly, the phrase "The mantle is of a beautiful, slightly purplish rose" completely excludes the possibility of attributing the Epsilon form of *H. alonensis* to the Cabo de Gata *Iberus* snails (currently identified as *I. xerophilus*), as these snails have a white mantle (see Liétor et al., 2024a and 2025a). It appears that CRA may be selectively and wrongly interpreting the historic data available in an effort to reclassify *I. alonensis*, which could, in turn, challenge the validity of *I. xerophilus*. We strongly recommend that the reader examine the taxonomic histories of *I. alonensis*, *I. rhodopeplus* ssp., and *I. xerophilus* presented in Liétor et al. (2025a).

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Paragraph 4

CRA: “A useful neotype designation is proposed herein in order to ensure stability in the identity and type locality of *Helix alonensis*”.

SA: The holotype and paratypes of *I. xerophilus* already exist and can be consulted in Liétor et al. (2024a).

CRA: “The neotype is properly curated and accessible for study in the author’s research collection”.

SA: We have already shown that CRA did not respond to a request for information about one of his holotypes. Therefore, actually, they could be not accessible.

Paragraph 7

CRA: “*Iberus (Alonensis) alonensis* is restricted to the area of Cabo de Gata, from Retamar in the west to Níjar in the north, and Las Negras in the northeast”.

SA: Incorrect. The populations of *I. xerophilus* (not *I. alonensis*) reach the municipal term of Vera, north of Almería, passing through the Sierra de Cabrera.

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Paragraph 9

CRA: “*Iberus (Valentiberus) alvaradoi* is the only species in extends from extreme eastern Murcia province, through the southern and central València region”.

SA: In Liétor et al. (2025a), ample evidence is provided to justify that the species referred to here as *I. alvaradoi* is a synonym of *I. alonensis*.

Paragraph 11

CRA: Making reference to *Iberus (Valentiberus) alvaradoi turoleensis* subsp. nov.- “Diagnosis.- More globose than other subspecies; spire just moderately depressed, last whorl comparatively tall and a bit bulging below”.

SA: After studying material from 94 populations across 10 different Spanish provinces, Liétor et al. (2025a) consider the available information insufficient to reliably undertake the taxonomic study of *I. alonensis* (erroneously referred to by CRA as *I. alvaradoi*). Preliminary genetic and morphological data lead the authors to suspect the existence of two subspecies, one in the north and one in the south, but many more samples would be needed to confirm this hypothesis and establish with some precision the distribution of these potential subspecies and their spatial limits. In contrast, CRA decides to describe 3 subspecies based on highly variable conchological traits, without specifying the number of specimens or locations sampled, not to mention that he assigns these subspecies to other pre-existing taxa in GenBank, presumably based on geographical location. We must point out that many of the coordinates recorded in GenBank for taxa of the genus *Iberus* (such as those from Elejalde et al., 2008a, b) correspond to UTM grids of 10 x 10 km², which implies significant uncertainty if we intend to assign neighboring subspecies within those grids. Regarding the conchological traits supporting this subspecies assignment, they lack strong backing in a field where numerous publications emphasize that the shell of terrestrial gastropods should not be used as the sole taxonomic criterion.

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Paragraph 7

CRA: Making reference to *Iberus (Valentiberus) alvaradoi ilercaonus* subsp. nov.- “Diagnosis.- The spire is higher than in other subspecies, and the last quarter whorl is slightly more expanded and consequently the aperture more rounded”.

SA: Just to give the reader an understanding of the degree of intraspecific variability in the shells of the genus *Iberus*: The coefficient of variation of the morphometric parameters measured on 757 *I. alonensis* shells (here wrongly called *I. alvaradoi*) from 63 sampling sites, ranged between 11 and 26% (see Liétor et al., 2025a). The variation in shell height, shell diameter, or peristome referred to by CRA likely falls well within the expected range of intraspecific variability.

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Paragraph 4

CRA: Making reference to *Iberus (Valentiberus) alvaradoi quixotei* subsp. nov.- “Type material. - Spain, Castilla-La Mancha, Ciudad Real province, Campo de Montiel county, Ruidera, 38°58' N, 2° 53' W, ca. 820 m; 12.x.2015, J. Liétor col. Holotype CRA-15746, diameter 26.4 mm”.

SA: J. Liétor has no record of having provided CRA with such holotype for the mentioned locality. Furthermore, J. Liétor does not provide shells with geographical coordinates. Therefore, the traceability of this alleged holotype is compromised.

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Paragraph 10

CRA: “The comments aiming at invalidating this genus by Jowers et al. (2024) and Liétor et al. (2024b) are crude misrepresentations, as *Tartessiberus* cannot be synonymized with *Iberus* without completely ignoring the tribe’s phylogeny, and the description of *T. cilbanus* was quite detailed and based on all morphological traits”.

SA: On one hand, as already mentioned, taxonomic studies based solely on anatomical characters are a practice of the past, especially if they are not integrated into a multidisciplinary approach that includes geography, morphology, and genetics. In the case of *Iberus*, Liétor et al. (2025a) have amply demonstrated how hybridization, which is so common in the genus *Iberus*, compromises the validity of anatomical studies. The lack of anatomical studies in our publications during 2024 and 2025 was a recurring concern raised by various reviewers. However, all of them acknowledged that the widespread hybridization within the genus *Iberus* was a significant factor that could compromise the validity of any study on genitalia. If the readers look at the phylogenetic tree provided by CRA in Figure 1, they will see that the branches of *Tartessiberina* for *Tartessiberus cilbanus* are remarkably short and close to the rest of the supposed species of the purported *Marmoratus* genus. Since the nodes are blurred and genetic distances are not indicated, based solely on the topology of this clade, it appears that all taxa are conspecific. However, CRA describes two genera.

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Paragraph 9

CRA: Making reference to *Angustiberus maginensis* spec. nov.- “Diagnosis. - A small allognathine belonging to *Angustiberus*, differing conspicuously from congeners in its almost open, clearly wider, more perspective and eccentric umbilicus. The spire is similar to that of depressed specimens of *A. hispanicus*, but the last whorl is somewhat more expanded”.

SA: Variation in the degree of umbilicus opening is common in *I. angustatus*, even within the same population (see Liétor et al., 2025a, p. 51). Therefore, it is largely unsuitable to use it as a taxonomic trait.

Paragraph 3

CRA: “*Angustiberus maginensis* sp. nov. appears to be restricted to Sierra Mágina, a mountain range in the Subbaetic Massif”.

SA: Liétor et al. (2025a) provide enough data to demonstrate that all the studied populations of *I. angustatus* belong to the same single species.

Paragraph 9

CRA: Making reference to *Helix (Helicogena) marmorata*- “*Iberus serpentinae* Ahuir Galindo, 2020 is a junior (subjective) synonym of this species. Its type locality is just a few kilometers to the west of Gaucín (Ahuir Galindo, 2020), the type locality of *M. marmoratus*, from which it cannot be discriminated”.

SA: This is not true. Liétor et al. (2024c), based on genetic distances and ecological requirements, modified the current taxonomic status of *I. serpentinae* to *I. marmoratus serpentinae*, which is the currently accepted designation on [Molluscabase](#).

Paragraph 1

CRA: “I consider *partschi* as a subspecies of *M. marmoratus*. Specimens from this area are similar to others from the eastern part of the species range (Fig. 18), in being smaller and with a more compact build-up in comparison with those from the remaining of the species distribution. Thus, *Marmoratus (M.) marmoratus partschi* (Servain, 1881) is the name applicable to the eastern set of populations of this species”.

SA: See Liétor et al. (2025a, p. 146-147) for the correct taxonomic status of *H. partschi*.

Paragraph 2

CRA: “Specimens from the northwestern edge of the range of *M. marmoratus* uniformly exhibit a distinctive flattened morphology. To the southwest, a peripheral isolate is inhabited by unusually small specimens. These constant differences support the recognition of two further subspecies described below”.

SA: What does "constant differences" mean? When CRA makes categorical claims about the differentiation of his taxa based on conchological criteria, he seems to have the certainty derived from exhaustive biogeographical and morphometric analyses, which are not presented in his work. Until such data are made available, it must be assumed that CRA has access to only limited field information; consequently, establishing stable morphological criteria for entire taxa based on just a few shells appears premature and scientifically questionable.

Paragraph 4

CRA: “Two southern isolates show distinctive traits and are herein recognized as subspecies, in addition to the nominotypical one. One of these is *M. (M.) I. candoni* (Ahuir Galindo, 2021)”.

SA: The genetic analysis of a sample of *I. candoni* conducted by Liétor et al. (2025a) supports that it is a genetically distinct species from *I. loxanus* (10.8% distance for the COI gene). More samples will be needed to confirm this assertion. However, CRA only needs a few conchological traits to define a new subspecies.

Paragraph 5

CRA: “Specimens of *M. loxanus violaceus* (Rossmässler, 1854) differ from the nominotypical subspecies in having a strongly depressed spire, a noticeably flaring and more extended lip, a beautiful violet (fading away in dead specimens)...”.

SA: The presence of a purple or violet lip is a constant feature in several species of the genus *Iberus* (*I. angustatus*, *I. giennensis*, *I. marmoratus*, *I. loxanus*...). Does this mean we should define new subspecies for all of them? Clearly not. Liétor et al. (2025a) do not have field data to establish what percentage of these species may show lips with pinkish tones. These specimens are distributed seemingly randomly among the populations. It cannot be stated that this trait is attributable to specific populations or infraspecific taxa. In fact, specimens of *I. loxanus* with a pink or violet lip can be found throughout the Andalusian region, ranging from Darrical (Almería) to Lora de Estepa (Seville).

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Paragraph 7

CRA: Making reference to *Marmoratus* (*M.*) *marmoratus gaditanus* subsp. nov.- “Diagnosis. - A semiglobose, pale, very small local form of *M. marmoratus*”.

SA: Liétor et al. (2025a) determine that the average sizes of some *Iberus* species in determinate populations are usually the result of local adaptation. A great example is *I. gualtieranus*, whose original populations from the Sierra de Gádor show considerable sizes, exceeding 4 cm in many cases. However, populations likely introduced by the Romans in Jaén and Granada exhibit smaller shells, around 3 cm in diameter. These are ecotypes specially adapted to local conditions. In fact, it has long been recognized that body size in land snails is highly plastic, influenced by environmental factors such as snail density (Williamson et al., 1976). Body size, therefore, is a poor and probably equivocal criterion to define species. Unless genetic analyses indicate otherwise, there are no compelling reasons to designate the smaller *I. marmoratus* from Cádiz as a subspecies.

Paragraph 17

CRA: “Type species.- *Iberus rositai* Fez, 1950”.

SA: Liétor et al. (2025a) provide a thorough review of the complex and error-prone taxonomic history of *I. rositai*. They also address the equally problematic case of *I. loxanus*, whose type series is plagued by misidentifications and includes specimens belonging to several *Iberus* species—including the form traditionally referred to as *I. loxanus* from El Torcal de Antequera, which actually corresponds to a globose morph of *I. rositai*, designated by Liétor et al. (2025a) as *I. polymorphicus* f. *globularis*.

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Paragraph 8

CRA: “The holotype, well illustrated by García San Nicolás (1957: pl. xviii, fig. 63), exhibits a moderate peripheral keel. This attenuated sculpture sets it apart from *M. rositai*”.

SA: Approaching the study of *Iberus* from the Torcal de Antequera without a detailed geographical study and, above all, without genetic analyses of its populations, is a serious mistake. Genetic and morphological studies suggest that, in the Torcal, there is a polymorphic species (referred to by Liétor et al., 2025a, as *I. polymorphicus*), with three well-differentiated morphotypes. One of them exhibits the traits of the classic *I. gualtieroloxanus*, another the traits of the classic *I. rositai*, and the third has traditionally been assigned to *I. loxanus*. The

accumulated taxonomic errors regarding this ecotypic complex are explained in detail in Liétor et al. (2025a, p. 159-162).

Paragraph 9

CRA: “Such variation appears to have a geographical translation: a cline from more rounded shells in areas with moderate karstic development to strongly keeled specimens in the more rugged, core area of the small massif. Thus, the two forms are treated herein as subspecies: *M. (T.) r. rositai* (Fez, 1950) in the Torcal Alto (high zone), and *M. (T.) r. gualtieroloxanus* (García San Nicolás, 1957) in the Torcal Bajo (lower area)”.

SA: This issue has been thoroughly examined by Liétor et al. (2025a), with the crucial inclusion of the historical “*I. loxanus*” from El Torcal—an addition that fundamentally shifts the perspective from which the taxonomic history of *Iberus* in this region should be analyzed. The decision of CRA to consider two subspecies without addressing the complex taxonomic history of both, which is marred by errors, is not appropriate. Just to give the reader an idea of the tangled taxonomic history we are dealing with: *I. gualtieroloxanus* was described by García San Nicolás (1957) from a single bleached shell originally assigned to the Sierra de Gredos, which the author recklessly reassigns to the Torcal de Antequera. To make matters worse, CRA claims that this subspecies inhabits the Torcal Bajo. Liétor et al. (2025a) only report the existence of *I. polymorphicus* f. *globularis* (the former *I. loxanus* from Torcal) in the Torcal Bajo. Therefore, CRA's geographical assignment of *I. gualtieroloxanus* is senseless.

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Paragraph 1

CRA: Making reference to *Oretaniina* subtr. nov.- “Remarks.- The two genera included differ appreciably in shell form”.

SA: Liétor et al. (2025a) have extensively studied the populations of *I. guiraoanus* from the Sierras de Cazorla, Segura, and las Villas (Jaén), Alcaraz (Albacete), and Castril (Granada), without any conchological reasons to differentiate distinct taxa. It is true that the intraspecific genetic variability detected is surprisingly high. As Liétor et al. (2025a) stated, more extensive sampling and genetic analysis will be required to clarify this issue. Defining new species without adequate scientific support, solely based on vague morphological criteria from a limited or very limited number of specimens, only adds to the taxonomic confusion.

Paragraph 3

CRA: Making reference to *Oretanius* gen. nov. - “Diagnosis.- Small to mid-sized allognathines with very finely ribbed shell, rounded to barely keeled whorls, low conical to moderately depressed spire, and completely closed umbilicus”.

SA: CRA's approach appears inconsistent throughout his revision. On one hand, he emphasizes subtle conchological differences to define new species, while on the other, he places species with cryptic shells into different subtribes (*Oretaniina* and *Tartessiberina*), as seen in cases such as *I. loxanus*, *I. angustatus*, and *I. guiraoanus*, among others.

Paragraph 4

CRA: “Type species.- *Helix alcarazana* Rossmässler, 1854”.

SA: See Liétor et al. (2024b) for the taxonomic status of *I. alcarazanus*.

Paragraph 12

CRA: "The three new species (*Iberus giennensis*, *I. axarcianus* and *I. antikarianus*) described by Liétor et al. (2024a) appear to be an indistinguishable subset of populations belonging to *Oretanius alcarazanus*".

SA: Indeed, the species in clade 1 of the genus *Iberus* (see Liétor et al., 2024b) are essentially cryptic, but it is incorrect to claim that unequivocal conchological criteria cannot be established to differentiate these species. Differences in morphometric parameters at the metapopulation level and in the coloration of soft parts can be observed, even in the ratios of banding patterns. Perhaps these traits are not operational for the casual collector, but this is by no means a problem. Moreover, in page 194 in Liétor et al. (2024b), we provide this subhead "Differences between shells of *I. giennensis*, *I. axarciensis* and *I. antikarianus* spp. nov.", with a long list of characters useful to field differentiation of the three species. Moreover, in page 195 it can be found the subhead "Morphometric comparison among *I. giennensis*, *I. axarciensis* and *I. antikarianus* spp. nov. and other *Iberus* taxa geographically close with similar shells", with a detailed characterization of traits to distinguish these species from near and similar species.

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Paragraph 1

CRA (starting in page 33): "Remarkably, these authors explicitly acknowledge these three nominal species cannot be reliably identified, basing their descriptions on centroids in morphometric space, average proportions, and overlapping variation in coloration patterns, plus a molecular tree that is reported to have weak support in critical nodes (the sequences are not available, so the tree cannot be assessed)".

SA: We don't know what the author means by "critical nodes". In any case, the support for the nodes shown in Liétor et al. (2024b) ranges from 84% to 100%, which represents a very robust result defining 3 monophyletic species with very long branches. The sequences of the new species described by Liétor et al. (2024b) have been available on the National Library of Medicine website since June 2024:

For *I. giennensis* see <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/?term=Iberus+giennensis>

For *I. antikarianus* see <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/2620307608>

For *I. axarciensis* see <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/?term=Iberus+axarciensis>

CRA: Making reference to Liétor et al. (2024b): "They state that the average size differences are not diagnostic, and that only through molecular analysis could specimens be allocated to any of these species, but they do not provide any information as to what to look for: "All these species have to be identified by genetic distances rather than morphological features." The holotypes of the three nominal species surely look like *O. alcarazanus*, as virtually all the shells figured therein; they refer to taxa deserving to be listed as junior synonyms. However, these three species descriptions do not include any mention of a single diagnostic character, so they do not meet Art. 13.1.1 and are thus unavailable. Besides, Liétor et al. (2024a) state that *Helix alcarazana* should be rejected and substituted, but offer no valid reason for such action".

SA: The author insists on searching for diagnostic characters. He can use the geographic location of the taxa. If he finds a cryptic *Iberus* from this group in the south of Jaén, it will be *I. giennensis*; if he finds it in Peña de los Enamorados in Antequera or in Archidona, it will be *I. antikarianus*; and if he finds it in the north of the Axarquía in Málaga or in the south of the Sierra Gorda de Loja (Málaga), it will be *I. axarciensis*. In Annex 1 of Liétor et al. (2025a), CRA may check all the sampling locations with their geographic coordinates to know the multitude of sites for these three species. In Annex 2 of Liétor et al. (2025a), CRA may check hundreds of photos of shells

and living specimens of the three species. However, on page 52 of Liétor et al. (2025a), a diagnostic character is shown: the different mantle and foot colorations in the three species discussed here. It is entirely incorrect to claim that Liétor et al. (2024b) does not provide reasons for considering *I. alcarazanus* an invalid taxonomic designation, as they explicitly reference the study by Martínez-Ortí and Robles (2012), which substantiates this conclusion. Moreover, CRA can find a detailed explanation on this matter in Liétor et al. (2025a, pp. 75-76).

Paragraph 2

CRA: Making reference to *Oretanius axans* spec. nov.- "Type material. - Spain, Andalucía, Málaga province, Comarca de Antequera county, Antequera, lowland near the Torcal de Antequera, 36° 58' N, 4° 29' W, ca. 820 m; 12.x.2015, J. Liétor col. Holotype."

SA: Since the holotype was provided by J. Liétor, and after examining Fig. 21, we have no doubt that this taxon corresponds to a hybrid population between *I. polymorphicus* f. *globularis* and *I. marmoratus*, found in the areas surrounding the Torcal de Antequera. Therefore, everything else presented in the entry referring to *Oretanius axans* is compromised.

Paragraph 11

CRA: "*Oretanius axans* has a distribution limiting with that of *Marmoratus (Torcaliberus) rositai* at the base of the Torcal de Antequera. The overall similarity with the less keeled forms of the latter species was hypothesized to indicate possible hybridization with *M. loxanus* (Alonso & Ibáñez, 1978: fig. 9D, as *Iberus loxanus*), but that is a conjecture; there is no genetic trace of any such event (Elejalde et al., 2008a)".

SA: We again invite the author to examine the section of Liétor et al. (2025a) dedicated to *I. polymorphicus*. It will address all of his concerns regarding this taxonomic complex.

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Paragraph 11

CRA: Making reference to *Cazorliberus bovisstrini* spec. nov.- "Type material. - Spain, Andalucía, Jaén province, Sierra de Cazorla county, Cazorla, Cerrada del Utrero, 37° 55' N, 2° 55' W, ca. 950 m; 24.iv.2013, J. Liétor col. Holotype".

SA: As the collector of the holotype, J. Liétor states that, with the body of evidence available to date, this specimen corresponds to *I. guiraoanus*. This is thoroughly argued in Liétor et al. (2025a).

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Paragraph 3

CRA: Making reference to *Cazorliberus cazorlensis* spec. nov.- "Diagnosis. - A small allognathine with partially closed umbilicus (more so than its congeners), and dark coloration with obscure bands".

SA: What differences does CRA see between his specimens in Fig. 22 and 23, which he claims belong to different species? Keep in mind that the expansion of the lip in the specimen from Figure 22 at the umbilical region is partially broken, so the degree of coverage of the umbilicus in both shells is the same, typical for the species. In fact, Liétor et al. (2025a) did not find a single specimen of *I. guiraoanus* with a partially open umbilicus among a total of 343 measured shells.

Paragraph 5

CRA: Making reference to *Cazorliberus cazorlensis* spec. nov.- “Type material. - Spain, Andalucía, Jaén province, Sierra de Cazorla county, La Iruela, 37° 55' N, 2° 59' W, ca. 920 m, under live oak litter; 2.vii.2011, J. Liétor col. Holotype”.

SA: As the collector of the alleged holotype, J. Liétor states that, with the body of evidence available to date, this specimen corresponds to *I. guiraoanus*. This is thoroughly argued in Liétor et al. (2025a).

Paragraph 11

CRA: “The revised taxonomy of the Allognathini is thus summarized (only native Iberian species mentioned; species-level taxa having neotypes and lectotypes designated herein are indicated by N or L, respectively)”.

SA: Given the substantial number of errors and methodological flaws outlined in the preceding pages, this taxonomy lacks credibility and is fundamentally unreliable, at least in its application to the genus *Iberus*.

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Table legend

SA: The reference DQ822150 is repeated 7 times, and the reference DQ822140 is repeated twice. The references DQ822214 and AY928500 correspond to bacteria. These errors compromise the reliability of the phylogenetic tree on which the taxonomic review is based. It is notable that CRA overlooks nearly all the genetic sequences uploaded to GenBank by Liétor et al. (2024a-c, g, 2025b) and Tudela et al. (2024). Nevertheless, CRA relies on the sequences provided by the authors in Jowers et al. (2024) for *Tartessiberus cilbanus*. While it is reasonable that all available data should be considered when constructing a phylogenetic tree, CRA appears to selectively choose sequences based on a criterion that remains unclear to us.

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Figure legend

SA: The image is blurry and pixelated when zoomed in. The nodes and short branches are not discernible. The poor quality of the image makes it impossible to interpret the legend in the graph.

Conclusions

Until our works, compiled in Liétor et al. (2025a), the genus *Iberus* had not been studied comprehensively. The integrative approach, which included systematic sampling across the entire southeastern Iberian Peninsula with more than 1,700 sampling sites, morphometric analysis of nearly 20,000 shells, and the incorporation of three genetic markers (two mitochondrial and one nuclear) for over 70 new genetic samples from key localities, allowed Liétor et al. (2025a) to thoroughly revise and reorganize the genus taxonomically. Their study confirmed species that had been described based on genetic evidence and reassigned others that had previously been classified solely on anatomical or conchological traits.

It is evident that any scientific study can be improved, so we welcome any new datasets that, based on a solid methodology, enhance the understanding of *Iberus* or correct any of our conclusions. However, this is not the case with CRA's review, as its methodology suffers from

numerous errors and fails to provide new field data (no new geographic records, no morphometric measurements, and no new biological samples are presented).

Furthermore, throughout the pages of our review, ample evidence is provided to demonstrate that many of CRA's arguments for reassigning currently accepted taxonomic designations—validated by scientific publications—lack scientific basis or, worse, are incorrect or outright false.

For all these reasons, we strongly recommend that the taxonomic decisions and conclusions presented in the article “Taxonomic revision of the Iberian Allognathini (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Helicidae)” be disregarded and not incorporated into international taxonomic records.

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